

CHEMISTRY SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF CO₂ EXTRACT FROM THE MIXTURE OF SPICES WITH HIGH CONTENT OF BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE COMPONENTS AND NATURAL FLAVORS IN THE PREPARATION OF CERTAIN TYPES OF FOOD PRODUCTS

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Abstract

The article presents the data regarding the selection as raw materials - spices with increased content of biologically active substances and natural flavors.

As a result, the compositions of mixtures of spices with increased content of biologically active components and natural flavors were developed for obtaining CO₂-extract, as well as the use of CO₂-extracts in the preparation of certain types of products.

The recipes were elaborated and samples of pate were prepared from chicken liver with the addition of CO₂-extract from the mixture of spices with an increased content of biologically active substances and natural flavors.

Keywords: spices, CO₂-extracts, biologically active substances, pate.

1. Introduction

Currently, there is a growing consumer trend towards food products with bioactive properties that provide beneficial effects to the human body in terms of promoting a healthy lifestyle. Natural bioactive components are necessary to obtain adequate functional food products, which play an essential role in improving health, maintaining well-being, improving immunity.

Therefore, the food fields have an increased interest in obtaining natural bioactive components that can be used as functional food ingredients or nutraceuticals.

Spices can be defined as a class of aromatic or strongly flavored substances obtained from plants, commonly used as condiments and used for their flavors and preservative qualities. Both individual spice extracts and their mixtures are used to add flavor, stimulate appetite, and impart preservative and therapeutic effects to food products. The most commonly used

spices for extraction are: black pepper, thyme, allspice, cinnamon, garlic, ginger, onion, chives, etc.

The industrial application of dry spices is sometimes difficult. An excellent alternative to dry spices is the use of extracts obtained by the CO₂-supercritical extraction method. These extracts have several advantages, such as: long storage time, comparative simplicity of the technology of incorporating them into the finished product, sterility, more efficient use of the substances contained in them.

In order to widen the range of food products, extraction products are incorporated into traditional recipes, thus enriching the flavor (taste and smell), the biological and nutritional value of the food.

Extracts from vegetable raw materials can be used to enrich food products with bioactive components, fat-soluble vitamins, natural antioxidants, natural flavors (taste and smell) and other compounds, which are miss-

ing in increasingly refined products. Extracts can be included as ingredients in the recipes of bakery products, glazes, creams, soufflés, syrups, drinks, fillings, preserves, meat products.

2. Materials and methods

Research is focused on:

- the selection of raw materials of vegetable origin (seeds, spices and herbs, etc.) and the analysis of the physico-chemical composition, for the production of the mixture of spices with an increased content of biologically active components and natural flavors;
- elaboration of recipes for spice mixtures with increased content of biologically active components and natural flavors for the manufacture of CO₂-extracts;
- production in laboratory conditions CO₂-extracts with increased content of biologically active components and natural flavors;
- determining the organoleptic and physico-chemical characteristics of CO₂-extracts;
- the development of recipes and the production in laboratory conditions of chicken pâtés with added CO₂-extracts from the mixture of spices rich in biologically active components and natural flavors.

The determination of the organoleptic and physico-chemical characteristics of CO₂-extracts were carried out according to the normative documents:

- Method for determining the acidity index, according to SR EN ISO 3596:2002 GOST R 51481-99;
- Method for determining the peroxide index, according to SR EN ISO 3960:2009.

3. Results and discussions

Based on research, four types of spices with increased content of biologically active components and natural flavors were selected: coriander, allspice, thyme and black pepper.

Following the comparative physico-chemical analysis between the selected vegetable raw materials, it was found [1-5]:

1. Coriander:

- rich in: proteins and lipids; S and P; Se and Zn; monounsaturated fatty acids; vitamin C, vitamin B₂ and B₁;
- poor in: carbohydrates; Mn; saturated fatty acids; vitamin B₃.

2. Allspice:

- rich in: carbohydrates; Na; polyunsaturated fatty acids, namely ω -6 fatty acids; vitamin C and B₃;
- poor in: protein, dietary fiber; K, Mg, S and P; Fe, Cu, Se and Zn; monounsaturated fatty acids, as well as ω -3 fatty acids; vitamins B₆, B₉, B₁, B₂ and A.

3. Thyme:

- rich in: dietary fiber, ash; Ca and Mg; Fe; saturated fatty acids; vitamins C, PP, B₆, B₁ and A;
- poor in: phytosterols.

4. Black pepper:

- rich in: K, Mn, Cu and F; phytosterols; ω -3 fatty acids; vitamins K and B₆;
- poor in: lipids, ash; Ca and Na; polyunsaturated fatty acids, ω -6 fatty acids.

3 recipes of spice mixture with increased content of biologically active components and natural flavors were developed for obtaining CO₂-extracts (table 1).

Table 1.

Recipes of spice mixtures

Nr.	The name of the spice	The taste of the spice	Ratio of the spice in the recipe, %		
			Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
1	Coriander	Sweet	89	50	44
2	Allspice	Bitter	10	-	26
3	Thyme	Flavored	-	40	26
4	Black pepper	Spicy	1	10	4

The recipes for the spice mix were selected based on taste and the process of extracting lipids and flavors from the raw material. The lipid content of coriander is over 25%, and this helps to extract the maximum amount of native substances from other spices. Coriander therefore predominates in the mix.

Depending on the taste and flavors of the spices it is important to dose the amount of each spice, the

sweetest/smooth spices will be present in larger quantity than the strong flavored spices [6].

At the installation for CO₂-supercritical extraction, model HA 120-50-01, three CO₂-samples were obtained - extracts from a mixture of spices, according to the recipes developed at optimal supercritical extraction regimes.

Figure 1. Samples of CO₂-extracts from the mixture of spices

For the use of CO₂-extraction in food products, sample three was selected from a mixture of coriander, allspice, thyme and black pepper.

The organoleptic indices of CO₂-extracts from the mixture of spices are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

The organoleptic characteristic of CO₂-extracts from the mixture of spices

Nr.	The name of the index	Characteristic
1	Appearance and consistency	Fat-soluble liquid or oily mass with a homogeneous consistency, from fluid at room temperature to unctuous (kept in a refrigerator $t=2$ °C), with or without waxy substances, without other impurities. Kept cold, it presents an uneven distribution of waxes in the volume of the product, which disappear easily after mixing and heating.
2	Transparency	Translucent at room temperature.
3	Color	Natural, characteristic color, from light brown with khaki-green shades to a dark brick shade.
4	Taste and smell	Pleasant smell, characteristic of the spices used, namely: coriander, allspice, thyme and black pepper; spicy, pleasant taste, strongly pronounced spices. Weak bitter aftertaste.

During the research, the physico-chemical indices of the CO₂-extract from the mixture of spices were determined, both from Separator I and from Separator II of the supercritical CO₂-extraction installation and are presented in table 3.

Table 3.

Physico-chemical indices of CO₂-extracts

Nr.	The name of the product	The acidity index, mg KOH/g extract	The peroxide index, mmol O ₂ /kg extract
1	CO ₂ -extracts from the mixture of spices	22,98	12,65

CO₂-extracts from the mixture of spices rich in biologically active components and natural flavors were used in the manufacture of pate from chicken liver.

CO₂-extracts from the mixture of spices obtained are more practical from a technological point of view than the actual use of spices, they have bactericidal, tonic properties, they improve the quality of food products, they have the characteristic flavor and taste of raw materials.

The basis of the entire assortment of pate was chicken liver and a mixture of fats: sunflower oil, cow butter, and as an ingredient of plant origin, rich in bio-active and flavoring compounds, CO₂-extract from the mixture of spices was used: coriander, allspice, thyme and black pepper.

The ratio of CO₂-extract from the mixture of spices in the elaborated chicken pate recipes was 0.07% and 0.10%.

Table 4.

Chicken liver pate recipes

Nr	Name of ingredients	Norm, %		
		Control	Recipe 1	Recipe 2
1	Minced chicken liver, blanched	58,10	58,30	58,30
2	Sunflower oil	30,00	29,93	29,90
3	Onion	5,00	5,00	5,00
4	Carrot	5,00	5,00	5,00
5	Salt for food use	1,30	1,30	1,30
6	Sugar	0,40	0,40	0,40
7	Spices (coriander, allspice, black pepper)	0,20	-	-
8	CO ₂ – spice extract mixture I	-	0,07	0,10
	Total	100,00	100,00	100,00

For a uniform distribution of the CO₂-extract in the mass of the chicken liver pate, the CO₂-extract from the mixture of spices was mixed with sunflower vegetable oil, in a ratio of 1.5: 30 ml.

Figure 2. Mixing CO₂-spice extract with sunflower vegetable oil

Chicken liver pate with the addition of CO₂-extract from the mixture of spices were tasted in the laboratory of Food Technology. All samples of prepared chicken liver pate were highly appreciated.

According to organoleptic evaluations, the most successful was pate from chicken liver with the addition of 0.07% of CO₂-extract from the mixture of spices: coriander 44%, allspice 26%, thyme 26% and black pepper 4%. This pate stood out for its savory flavor and taste of coriander and thyme and its dense consistency.

In the samples of pate with the addition of 0.2 % mixture of spice, their content is barely noticeable, it does not influence the organoleptic qualities.

For chicken liver pate with added CO₂-extract from the mixture of spices packed in glass jars with a capacity of 0.25 dm², the sterilization regime was developed: $\frac{25 - 70 - 25}{120}$

Chicken liver pate control sample

Chicken liver patties with the addition of mixed spices

Chicken liver patties with the addition of CO₂-extract of spices

Figure 3. Laboratory samples: Chicken liver pate

Thus, as a result of the research, a new food product was developed - chicken liver pate with added CO₂-extract from the mixture of spices with increased content of biologically active components and natural flavors.

Conclusions

1. The following assortment was selected as raw materials - spices with an increased content of biologically active substances and natural flavors for the production of CO₂-extract from thea mixture of spices: coriander, allspice, thyme, black pepper.

2. 3 recipes of mixtures of spices with increased content of biologically active components and natural flavors were developed for the manufacturing of CO₂-extract.

3. CO₂-extract samples with increased content of biologically active components and natural flavors were obtained under laboratory conditions.

4. The recipes were developed and samples of pate were prepared from chicken liver with the addition of 0.07% and 0.1% of CO₂-extract from the mixture of spices.

5. The sterilization mode for chicken liver pate with added CO₂-extract from the mixture of spices packed in glass jars with a capacity of 0.25 dm³ was developed.

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